

Insect resistance

Mixing rice varieties to combat brown planthopper

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Various mixtures of two rice varieties – one resistant to brown planthopper (BPH) damage and one susceptible – were grown to study the relationship between the mixtures and damage by insects. RD7, a susceptible variety, and RD9, which carries the *Bph 1* resistance gene, were used. Both are high yielding, semidwarf types; RD9 matures slightly earlier.

Mixed seeds were germinated in petri dishes and planted in wooden flats; at the two-leaf stage, heavy populations of first-instar BPH were released to infest the seedlings for 10 days. The RD7 population was 100% damaged; the RD9 population was undamaged. In a mixture of 50% RD7 and 50% RD9, 82% of the plants were undamaged; in a mixture containing 66.7% RD9 plants, 72% were undamaged. Random combinations of environmental variables may have affected results, but the data suggest that introducing at least a 50% portion of resistant plants into a susceptible population may reduce damage to levels lower than that expected on the basis of the ratios of the varieties.

Breeding for resistance to brown planthopper and grassy stunt in Kerala, India

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Breeding for resistance to the brown planthopper and the associated grassy stunt virus has been under way at the Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India, since 1974. During 1975, bulked

progenies in F₄ were tested under field conditions at Pattambi, Moncombu, and Mannuthy. These progenies were also tested at the seedling stage under greenhouse conditions at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program, Hyderabad, and 400 selections were identified as tolerant or resistant to brown planthopper on the basis of both field and greenhouse observations. Those 400 lines (see table) were grown in an observational trial during the first crop season of 1976.

Parentage of 400 rice lines identified as resistant or tolerant to the brown planthopper and grown in an observational trial at Pattambi, India, 1976.

Parentage	Lines (no.)
Bharathi/IR2071-625-2-1	103
Triveni/IR2061-461	75
Triveni/Mudgo	96
Triveni/IR1539	126

A crossing program has been undertaken with donors for brown planthopper resistance that are thought to be most appropriate for the Kerala region. Fifty-five crosses involving the varieties PTB 33, PTB 18, PTB 21, and others as sources of resistance were accomplished during 1975.

Deep water

Screening for kneeing ability

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Rice plants usually lodge after the internodes have elongated and floodwaters have receded. Deep-water varieties must have kneeing ability to keep the first three leaves above the water level, preventing leaf decay and providing better leaf arrangement. Kneeing also bears the panicle above the reach of fishes.

A system for scoring the kneeing ability of deep-water rice cultivars.

To test for kneeing ability, use a puddled and leveled field, and rice plants at least 60 days old. Dig carefully around the base of each rice plant and pull out the plant gently. Use four plants for each variety. Lay each plant horizontally on the puddled field. Label. Randomize the varieties to be tested. Maintain water depth at 2 cm. The plants tend to move around or roll if the water is too deep. On the eighth day, score for kneeing ability (see figure).